

D5.2: An international code of conduct for data sharing in genomics: A proposal

[WP5 – The Consortium’s Proposals]

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Due date	1 st , February, 2021
Delivery date	28 Feb, 2021 (report)
Embargo	Embargo for publication until August 31, 2021
Type	Report
Dissemination level	PU = Public

Keywords Data sharing, genomics, big data, cloud computing services, broad consent

The SIENNA project - *Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact* - has received funding under the European Union’s H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 741716.

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Abstract

As part of the SIENNA consortium proposals (WP5), the deliverable proposes an international code of conduct for data sharing in genomics. It builds on results of D 2.3: Survey of REC approaches and codes for genomics, D2.4: Ethical analysis of human genetics and genomics and D5.6: Recommendations for the enhancement of the existing legal frameworks for genomics, human enhancement, and AI and robotics.

To draft the proposed code of conduct, we adopted a mix of methods involving a literature review, synthesis of pertinent existing codes of conduct, a workshop of an expert panel and soliciting feedback from SIENNA stakeholders.

The deliverable addresses specific concerns and gaps as identified via literature namely; identifiability, broad consent, portability accessibility and return of results, compelled disclosure and lastly withdrawal of consent. Furthermore, we propose mitigation measures as recommended by experts and stakeholders and through synthesis of relevant past codes. The results have been discussed in the light of GDPR which is the most relevant legal framework within the EU.

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Reason for change	Distribution
V0.1	20 08 2020	First Draft	A preliminary draft to get input on	11 09 2020
V0.2	18 12 2020	Second draft	Input from expert panel	04 01 2021
V0.3	28 01 2021	Third Draft	Input from stakeholders and scientific advisory board	01 02 2021
V0.4	22 02 2021	Final Version	Input from Q & A reviewers	26 02 2021

Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
Task 6.1	This report employed stakeholder engagement in drafting code of conduct within HGG technology. It made use of stakeholders' list created in D1.2 and can support generalising methods for stakeholder engagement in D6.1.
Task 6.3	D 5.2 is an example that can feed into a step-by-step guidance from ethical analysis to ethical codes and operational guidelines task.

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Executive summary

Introduction

This report is generated as a fulfilment of a European Commission (EC) funded SWAFS¹ project called [SIENNA](#), which started in October 2017. The project is tasked with addressing Ethical, Legal, Social Implications (ELSI) in three emerging technology areas: Human Genomics and Genetics (HGG), AI & Robotics and Human Enhancement Technology.

As part of SIENNA consortium proposals WP5, the deliverable proposes an international code of conduct for data sharing in genomics. It builds on results of D 2.3: Survey of REC approaches and codes for genomics², D2.4: Ethical analysis of human genetics and genomics³ and D5.6: Recommendations for the enhancement of the existing legal frameworks for genomics, human enhancement, and AI and robotics⁴.

Methods

The work for this deliverable began with a main goal which is to create a document that will fulfil a need within the field and be useful to HGG stakeholders. This was achieved by a mix of methods:

- 1- Determining gaps in the current professional best practices and identifying a need for a code of conduct (CoC) within the HGG field – through a literature review and consulting past HGG SIENNA deliverables (2.3, 2.4, 5.6).
- 2- Synthesis of existing professional codes that address biological data and specimen use to develop a preliminary draft of the CoC.
- 3- Using the SIENNA approach to involve expert stakeholders in the process of refining the proposed draft. The stakeholders' input was obtained by conducting a workshop (held on 10th September, 2020) with an expert panel of genomics and data sharing experts in order to get their input and views on a preliminary draft.
- 4- The method can be described as reiterative, because we involved other stakeholders: SIENNA scientific advisory board (via workshop on 14th January, 2021) and SIENNA expert stakeholders, who were directly contacted via email, to review and suggest amendments to the proposed CoC. Six out of 15 contacted responded to our request for feedback.

¹ [SWAFS: Science with and for Society](#)

² Howard, Heidi C, et al., "Sienna D2.3: Survey of REC Approaches and Codes for Genomics", 2019, pp. 1-36. pp. 1- 36 [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4066865](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4066865)

³ Alexandra Soulier, Emilia Niemiec and Heidi Carmen Howard, *Sienna D2.4: Ethical Analysis of Human Genetics and Genomics*, 2019. <https://zenodo.org/record/4068016>. pp. 1- 166 [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4068016](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4068016)

⁴ Siemaszko, Konrad , Rowena Rodrigues and Santa Slokenberga, *Sienna D5.6: Recommendations for the Enhancement of the Existing Legal Frameworks for Genomics, Human Enhancement, and Ai and Robotics*, 2020. <https://zenodo.org/record/4121082>. Pp. 1- 72 [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4121082](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4121082)

Preliminary Results and Discussion

The deliverable describes specific concerns and gaps as identified in the literature namely; identifiability, broad consent, portability accessibility and return of results, compelled disclosure and lastly withdrawal of consent. Furthermore, we propose mitigation measures as recommended by experts and stakeholders and through synthesis of relevant past codes.

Though the proposed CoC aims to address best practices in international genomic data-sharing, the report discussed the concerns and gaps in a European context taking in consideration GDPR provisions. The CoC itself is not a legal document but an ethical one.

The CoC

The proposed CoC aims to cover a data cycle, which we defined as a process that starts by data collection from donors, going through a series of stages of data storage; sharing and transfer; access and use; and lastly returning of results to data donors. These steps are managed and linked together by a governance system. The latter is managed by a data management committee (DMC). Furthermore, the CoC addresses community engagement and data handling in Low-and -Middle-Income Countries.

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI & robotics	Artificial intelligence & robotics
BRICS	Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa
CIOMS	Council for International Organisations of Medical Sciences
CoC	Code of conduct
CSP	Cloud service providers
DAC	Data access committee
DMC	Data management committee
DPA	Data protection act (of the UK).
DPIA	Data protection impact analysis
DPO	Data protection officer
EDPB	The European Data Protection Board
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HET	Human enhancement technology
HGG	Human genomics and genetics
HUGO	Human Genome Organisation
LMIC	Low-and-middle income countries
NSA	National Security Agency
OECD	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SCC	Standard contractual clauses
SCC	Sub-contractual clauses
ToR	Terms of reference
ToS	Terms of service

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
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Aggregate data	A collection of data that have been re-expressed by a summary statistic ⁵ .
Anonymous information	anonymous information does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. The GDPR does not therefore concern the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes. (GDPR Recital 26) ⁶
Broad consent	“The GDPR allows for the possibility that when scientific research involves collecting personal data, it may be impossible to fully specify the precise purposes of any data processing in advance. Therefore, data subjects should be allowed to give their consent to certain areas of scientific research when in keeping with recognised ethical standards for scientific research” ⁷ .
Controller	“The natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data” (GDPR Art 4 (7)).
Data cycle	This describes the flow of data from a data subject through data storage, access, use and sharing and until relevant findings and results are communicated back to a data subject.
Data subject	For the purpose of this document, a data subject is the person who donates his/her genomic data or biospecimens or partakes in genomics research.
Incidental findings	“A finding concerning an individual research participant that has a potential health or reproductive importance and is discovered in the course of conducting research or diagnostic procedures but is beyond the aims of the study” ⁸ .
Processing of data	“Any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction” (GDPR Art 4 (2)).

⁵American Psychology Association Dictionary of Psychology, *Aggregate Data*, 2020.
<https://dictionary.apa.org/aggregate-data>.

⁶ European Parliament and Council of European Union, General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679
<https://gdpr-info.eu/>

⁷ Molnár-Gábor, Fruzsina and Jan O Korbelt, "Genomic Data Sharing in Europe Is Stumbling—Could a Code of Conduct Prevent Its Fall?," *EMBO molecular medicine*, Vol. 12, No. 3, 2020, pp. e11421.

⁸ As defined in Wolf, Susan M, et al., "Managing Incidental Findings in Human Subjects Research: Analysis and Recommendations", *The Journal of Law, Medicine & Ethics*, Vol. 36, No. 2, 2008, pp. 219-248.

Processor	“A natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller” (Art 4 (9)).
Pseudonymisation	“Means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person” (Art 4(5)).

Table 2: Glossary of terms

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

This report fulfils the deliverable of 5.2 as part of WP5: The consortium’s proposals. The objectives of the work package are to augment current ethical guidelines for review of research as well as professional codes with functioning components in the three technology areas, Human Genetics and Genomics (HGG), Artificial Intelligence and Robotics (AI & robotics) and Human Enhancement Technology (HET). The D 5.2 aims to create a code of conduct (CoC) for researchers in genomics.

1.2 Objectives

The main objectives for this deliverable are:

- 1- Determine a gap in existing professional codes of conduct in genomics.
- 2- Identify a need for another professional code of conduct in HGG.
- 3- Generate a code of conduct that addresses a need within HGG and would be useful to the field.

1.3 Structure of the report

The report is organized as follows:

1. The first section describes the background to the deliverable in relation to SIENNA handbook and previous relevant SIENNA deliverables in HGG. It also delineates the main objectives and the scope of the intended work. Lastly, we discuss some of the limitations and obstacles encountered during the course of producing the report.
2. Section two outlines the method that has been utilized in generating the proposal for the CoC.
3. Section three gives a short account of “how to write a CoC” as has been addressed in SIENNA handbook D1.1⁹ and some relevant literature.
4. The fourth section is a description of the motivation behind drafting the CoC and a short discussion of literature in relation to preliminary results obtained from the expert panel workshop.
5. Section five proposes the CoC for international data sharing in genomics.
6. The last section presents conclusions, future steps and key messages to consider in relation to the CoC proposal.

⁹ Jensen, Sean R, et al., "D1. 1: The Consortium’s Methodological Handbook", 2019, pp. pp. 69- 78. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4247384](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4247384)

1.4 Scope and limitations

This is a proposal for a code of conduct for international data sharing in genomics. The CoC is relevant for genomic researchers, research institutes and cloud computing services/databases that store and / or handle genomic data.

There are a few limitations to this report which can be categorized as practical and methodological. Due to practical shortcomings as the lack of time and limited workforce, we could not engage more stakeholders in the process of formulating the code of conduct. Input from genomic researchers, IT professionals, data protection officers and research participants / data subjects on the proposed CoC would have been quite valuable. In addition, a wider geographical representation of experts especially from Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMIC) would have enriched the CoC further. Furthermore, Human Genomics and Genetics (HGG) is a well-established field with a large number of ethical guidelines and best practice documents¹⁰. Therefore, it was challenging to identify an actual need within HGG without a risk to become redundant or repetitive.

2. Methodology

To develop this code of conduct, we adopted a mixed method approach which involved,

- 1- Determining the gaps in current professional codes of conduct and identifying a need for a CoC within the HGG field – through a literature review and consulting past HGG SIENNA deliverables (2.1¹¹, 2.3¹², 2.4¹³, 5.6¹⁴).
- 2- Synthesizing of existing professional codes that address biological data and specimen use to develop a preliminary draft of the CoC (refer below to the list of documents). The list was selected via a literature review and some documents were suggested by stakeholders.
- 3- Using the SIENNA approach to involve stakeholders in the process of refining the proposed draft, an expert panel meeting was held on 10th September, 2020, to discuss the proposed CoC and obtain input on gaps as identified in the literature. The panel was constituted of genomics and data sharing experts including physicians, a scientist, lawyers, bioethicists and a

¹⁰ Howard, Heidi C, Emilia Niemiec, Lisa Tambornino and Dirk Lanzerath, op.cit., 2019. [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4066865](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4066865)

¹¹ Howard, Heidi C, Emilia Niemiec and Alexandra Soulier, *Sienna D2.1: State of the Art Review of Human Genomic Technologies*, 2019. <https://zenodo.org/record/4067912>. [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4067912](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4067912)

¹² Howard, Heidi C, Emilia Niemiec, Lisa Tambornino and Dirk Lanzerath, op.cit., 2019. [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4066865](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4066865)

¹³ Alexandra Soulier, Emilia Niemiec and Heidi Carmen Howard, op.cit., 2019. [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4068016](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4068016)

¹⁴ Siemaszko, Konrad , Rowena Rodrigues and Santa Slokenberga, op.cit., 2020. pp 23. [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4121082](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4121082)

sociologist. Follow up questions were sent to the expert panel in November, 2020 and input on a second draft of the CoC was sought (refer to Annex 1).

- 4- The method was reiterative, involving other stakeholders: SIENNA scientific advisory board (via a workshop on 14th January, 2021) and SIENNA's stakeholder list (via email contact) to review and suggest further amendments to the proposed CoC. For more details about the selection of stakeholders and creation of the list, refer to SIENNA D 1.2¹⁵. A total of 15 persons received the CoC via email and 6 responded to our request. Only those who provided written feedback had their input first considered then incorporated into the CoC. The responders were lawyers, physicians and philosophers.

List of documents, ethics and professional codes that have been synthesized to draft this CoC (refer to figure 1)

- CoC for user access to the RD-Connect Genome-Phenome Analysis Platform (GPAP) for health-related information ¹⁶.
- BBMRI-ERIC for access to and sharing of biological samples and data¹⁷.
- International Charter of principles for sharing bio-specimens and data¹⁸
- WHO's CoC for open and timely sharing of pathogen genetic sequence data during outbreaks of infectious disease¹⁹.
- Ethical and legal issues of genomic cloud computing²⁰
- GFBR: ethics of data sharing and biobanking in health research²¹
- International code of conduct for genomic and health-related data sharing ²²

¹⁵ Rodrigues, Rowena and Stearns Broadhead, *D1.2: Stakeholder Analysis and Contact List*, 2018. pp. 1-30

¹⁶ Hansson, Mats G, et al., *Code of Conduct for User Access to the Rd-Connect Genome-Phenome Analysis Platform (Gpap) for Health-Related Information*, 2018. https://rd-connect.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/RD-Connect_Code-of-Conduct_GPAP_20180525.pdf. pp.1-8

¹⁷ BBMRI-ERIC, *BBMRI-ERIC Policy for Access to and Sharing of Biological Samples and Data*, 2017. https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/wp-content/uploads/AoM_10_8_Access-Policy_FINAL_EU.pdf.

¹⁸ Mascalzoni, Deborah, et al., "International Charter of Principles for Sharing Bio-Specimens and Data", *European Journal of Human Genetics*, Vol. 23, No. 6, 2015, pp. 721-728. pp. 1-6

¹⁹ World Health Organization, "World Health Organization's Code of Conduct for Open and Timely Sharing of Pathogen Genetic Sequence Data During Outbreaks of Infectious Disease", *WHO* <https://www.who.int/blueprint/what/norms-standards/gsdsharing/en>, 2019, pp. 1 - 6; *ibid*.

²⁰ Dove, Edward S, et al., "Genomic Cloud Computing: Legal and Ethical Points to Consider", *European Journal of Human Genetics*, Vol. 23, No. 10, 2015, pp. 1271-1278.

²¹ Hunt, Adrienne, *Meeting Report: Ethics of Data Sharing and Biobanking in Health Research*, 2018. <https://www.gfbr.global/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/GFBR-2018-meeting-report-FINAL.pdf>. pp. 1- 27

²² Sugano, Sumio, "International Code of Conduct for Genomic and Health-Related Data Sharing", *The HUGO Journal*, Vol. 8, No. 1, 2014, pp. 1-4.

- The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship ²³

Figure 1: Documents synthesized to draft the code of conduct

3. How to write a CoC?

A CoC and a code of ethics generally aspire to provide its users with guidance as to shared ethical values and best practices within a profession or an organisation. There is a distinction between the two. The latter elucidates general ethical values or principles to which an organization commits, (for example; transparency, accountability) while the former prescribes certain behaviours or actions in response to particular ethical challenges such as conflict of interest, bribery etc. Codes of ethics have

²³ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

been criticised for being vague and difficult to implement practically while codes of conduct can become quite detailed and bring attention only to what one *should not* do. Furthermore, a CoC can inadvertently make users furlough ethical judgement and personal responsibility. The inclination now is to incorporate “compliance” and “integrity” dimensions in ethical documents²⁴. In this report, we provide a set of principles that the CoC aspires to attain as well as delineate best practices for data sharing internationally.

Six stages (refer to figure 2) have been described to develop a CoC for a company or an organization in SIENNA handbook²⁵. The initial step is to gather information, which we obtained via a literature review and consulting relevant SIENNA deliverables (2.1²⁶, 2.3²⁷ and 2.4²⁸). Secondly, a draft is created that is, thirdly, reviewed by relevant actors such as an ethics officer, potential users or the management of the organisation. We accomplished this through the expert panel meeting and SIENNA’s scientific advisory board members and stakeholders. Upon making the necessary revisions per the input from stakeholders, the CoC can now be officially adopted by the organisation (stage four). Fifthly, it is important to disseminate the code to all potential users and allow time for training personnel or potential users on how to use the code. The last step is to enforce the code, a function that can be performed by an ethics officer in the organisation. Enforceability includes measures of monitoring and reporting of non-compliance as well as issuing disciplinary actions²⁹. It is worth noting that steps 4-6 are outside the scope of this deliverable.

²⁴ Gilman, Stuart C, "Ethics Codes and Codes of Conduct as Tools for Promoting an Ethical and Professional Public Service: Comparative Successes and Lessons", *Prepared for the PREM, the World Bank*, 2005, pp. pp. 12-18

²⁵ Jensen, Sean R, Heidi C Howard, Alexandra Soulier, Emilia Niemiec, Rowena Rodrigues, Stearns Broadhead and David Wright, op.cit., 2019.

²⁶ Howard, Heidi C, Emilia Niemiec and Alexandra Soulier, op.cit., 2019. [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4067912](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4067912)

²⁷ Howard, Heidi C, Emilia Niemiec, Lisa Tambornino and Dirk Lanzerath, op.cit., 2019. [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4066865](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4066865)

²⁸ Alexandra Soulier, Emilia Niemiec and Heidi Carmen Howard, op.cit., 2019. [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4068016](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4068016)

²⁹ Lighthouse, *Developing a Code of Conduct: A Step by Step Guide*, 2013. pp. 1-11

Figure 2 – Steps for developing a code of conduct adopted from Lighthouse

4. A proposal for an international code of conduct for data sharing in genomics

4.1 Background

The field of HGG generated a plethora of guidelines and codes of ethics both at national and international levels. SIENNA’s deliverable 2.3 comprehensively covered ethical guidelines and professional codes developed by professional organisations, ethics advisory groups, and research ethics committees within the field of HGG.

“One hundred and sixty-four documents which specifically address human genetics and/or genomics were retrieved from 11 countries where country studies were specifically performed: Brazil, China, France, Germany, Greece, The Netherlands, Poland, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. In addition, 22 documents from “international groups” like the OECD, or HUGO were also identified (between 2014-

2017); this includes documents from the USA since despite being issued at the national level, they often have worldwide recognition and/or impact”³⁰ pp. 489.

Within the field of HGG, it is therefore a challenge to identify a need for yet another code of conduct or ethical guidelines. However, an incident during the summer of 2020, brought the discussion of a need for a code of conduct for international data sharing in genomics to the forefront.

4.2 GDPR, international data transfer and genomic data

The Court of Justice of the European Union annulled the US-EU privacy shield agreement that regulated transfer of EU citizens’ data to USA in July, 2020³¹. Under that agreement transatlantic companies were permitted to uphold European data to better privacy standards before transfer to the US. However, this was pronounced as void due to the overreaching surveillance laws of the American national security and police enforcement, which allow access to people’s personal data with minimum restrictions^{32,33}. Consequently, from then onwards, all data including genomic data would require establishing another legal avenue for data transfer to the US.

According to the EU Court of Justice, not only is the Privacy Shield agreement void, but a Standard Contractual Clauses (SCC) would not be adequate as an alternative on its own, since regulators would have to guarantee “whether the law of the third country of destination ensures adequate protection under EU law”³⁴. There would be, in addition, a need for further safeguards measures such as codes of conducts. Indeed, matters would become more complicated after Brexit, since the UK would be required to fulfil privacy adequacy terms compatible to GDPR for data sharing as well³⁵. Fortunately, the Data Protection Act (DPA) of the UK shares significant resemblance to the GDPR³⁶.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) covers 27 EU member states and Norway, Iceland and Lichtenstein. Furthermore, the European Commission has found that 12 other countries meet either full or partial adequacy requirements, and therefore data can be shared with these states. They include; “Andorra, Argentina, Canada (only commercial organizations), Faroe Islands, Guernsey, Israel,

³⁰ Howard, Heidi C, Emilia Niemiec, Lisa Tambornino and Dirk Lanzerath, op.cit., 2019. [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4066865](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4066865)

³¹ Jacques, René Z, *The Court of Justice Invalidates Decision 2016/1250 on the Adequacy of the Protection Provided by the EU-US Data Protection Shield*, 2020. <https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/upload/docs/application/pdf/2020-07/cp200091en.pdf>. *ibid.*

³² *Ibid.*

³³ BBC, *EU - US Privacy Shield for Data Struck Down by Court*, 2020. <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-53418898>.

³⁴ Ordish, Johan and Alison Hall, "Impact of Schrems II on Sharing Genomic Data ", *PHG Foundation*, 2020, pp. 1-6.

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ Gov.UK, *Data Protection*, 2018. <https://www.gov.uk/data-protection>.

Isle of Man, Jersey, New Zealand, Switzerland, Uruguay and Japan. Data transfer to these countries is “expressly permitted”³⁷.

The GDPR is one major legal document that is mostly discussed in relation to data sharing across borders, within and outside the EU. Health related data generally and genomic data specifically are considered as “special categories of personal data” and therefore warrant special protections. However, if these data fall under the research category, they are rendered some flexibility³⁸.

In the context of genomic research, data subjects are granted certain rights under the GDPR. These include and not limited to; “the rights to information (Art 13, 14), data access (Art 15) and portability (Art 20), the rights to erasure (Art 17) and rectification of data (Art 16), rights to object (Art 21) and not be solely a subject to automated data processing (Art 22).”³⁹ Data processing in the context of research, including genomic research, enjoys some flexibility in GDPR, since they are of “public interest” (Art 9 (2))⁴⁰. These rights in genomics context have been subjected to thorough academic scrutiny (See for example ⁴¹).

While the global north negotiates legal complexities, the global south expresses fears and scepticism of sharing their data in international platforms. Researchers from the global south worry about exploitation of their efforts, data misuse and inequitable access to research benefits⁴². Indeed, there are already claims of data misuse through commercialization following data transfers from Africa to a host country⁴³. To assuage these fears, some researchers advocate measures such as building local capacities in disadvantaged data-donor nations, community engagement in the process of research and data transfer, and full transparency within international research endeavours⁴⁴.

³⁷ The European Commission, *Adequacy Decisions*, 2019. https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/international-dimension-data-protection/adequacy-decisions_en.

³⁸ European Parliament and Council of European Union, 2016/679

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ Mitchell, Colin, Johan Ordish and Alison Hall, "Genomic Medicine and Research: How Does the GDPR Apply", 2020, pp. 1-27.

⁴² Serwadda, David, et al., "Open Data Sharing and the Global South—Who Benefits?", *Science*, Vol. 359, No. 6376, 2018, pp. 642-643. pp. 642-643

⁴³ Moodley, Keymanthri and Anita Kleinsmidt, "Allegations of Misuse of African DNA in the UK: Will Data Protection Legislation in South Africa Be Sufficient to Prevent a Recurrence?", *Developing World Bioethics*, 2020, pp. 1- 6. pp.

⁴⁴ Serwadda, David, Paul Ndebele, M Kate Grabowski, Francis Bajunirwe and Rhoda K Wanyenze, op.cit., 2018.

The call for a code of conduct for data sharing internationally in genomics has been reiterated by academics, including bioethicists and lawyers^{45,46}. This is especially pertinent now with advent of big international genomic projects involving multinational partners⁴⁷ and the covid-19 pandemic that plead for faster and easier flow of genomic data⁴⁸. In a recent article by Phillips et al., specific questions were raised in the pursuit of a future code of conduct. According to the authors, there are unresolved concerns regarding consent procedures, return of results, data portability, compelled disclosure and identifiability⁴⁹.

In addition, a CoC may provide solutions to some of the legal concerns such as maintaining the privacy of personal data across borders, as asserted by Ordish & Hall⁵⁰. Furthermore, it could act as a framework for various nations, where little in terms of guidance (such as laws or regulations) exists, for example in LMICs⁵¹. However, the purpose of this proposal is not to solve GDPR legal complexities, this is better left to national capacity of academics, socio-political and legal institutions. It is to propose a document that ascribes to best practices in data sharing. It is worth noting that Biobanking and BioMolecular Research Infrastructure-European Research Infrastructure Consortium (BBMRI-ERIC) is in the process of drafting a GDPR CoC specific for health research⁵².

4.3 Preliminary results and discussion

As stated earlier, a workshop with an expert panel was conducted on 10th September, 2020. There were 16 attendees which included; lawyers, bioethicists, physicians, a sociologist, a representative from patient organizations, a scientist and research communicators. They represented EEA/EU countries and non-EEA/EU ones. The main purpose of the workshop was to get experts' views on a preliminary draft of a CoC as well as provide some answers to issues raised in the literature regarding international data sharing. In the following paragraphs, we discuss each issue in context of experts' input and the relevant literature.

⁴⁵Knoppers, Bartha Maria, et al., "Towards a Data Sharing Code of Conduct for International Genomic Research", *Genome Medicine*, Vol. 3, No. 7, 2011, pp. 1 - 4.

⁴⁶ Molnár-Gábor, Fruzsina and Jan O Korbelt, op.cit., 2020.

⁴⁷ Phillips, Mark, et al., "Genomics: Data Sharing Needs an International Code of Conduct", *Nature*, 2020, pp. 31- 33.

⁴⁸ Aguiar, Eric Rgr, Jesús Navas and Luis Gc Pacheco, "The Covid-19 Diagnostic Technology Landscape: Efficient Data Sharing Drives Diagnostic Development", *Frontiers in public health*, Vol. 8, 2020, pp. 1 - 4.

⁴⁹ Phillips, Mark, Fruzsina Molnár-Gábor, Jan O Korbelt, Adrian Thorogood, Yann Joly, Don Chalmers, David Townsend and Bartha M Knoppers, op.cit., 2020.

⁵⁰ Ordish, Johan and Alison Hall, op.cit., 2020.

⁵¹ Bull, Susan and Nireesh Bhagwandin, "The Ethics of Data Sharing and Biobanking in Health Research", *Wellcome open research*, Vol. 5, 2020, pp. 1 - 5.

⁵² Mitchell, Colin, Johan Ordish and Alison Hall, op.cit., 2020.

4.3.1 Identifiability

Genetic data are defined as personal identifiable data according to GDPR (article 4 (13); recital 34)⁵³ and as a “special category” data necessitating robust safeguard (Art 9)^{54,55}. This was corroborated by commentators and studies, which proved that genome sequence data can identify specific persons^{56,57}. To complicate matters further, with the expanding use of big databases whether they are genomics or health related, acquiring “richer” data will be made easier, which would further facilitate identification via cross-linking of various data inputs⁵⁸. Therefore, pseudonymisation and anonymisation may not be beneficial alone without extra organizational and technical means that render identification harder to attain⁵⁹.

Phillips and colleagues⁶⁰ brought forward specific concerns regarding identifiability in an international data sharing CoC. They stated that infringements to data privacy are sometimes elusive and difficult to account for because of the unclear chain of responsibility, particularly with the use of big transnational databases and cloud computing services. Moreover, lack of standardized terminology regarding identifiability leads to varying degrees of misunderstandings among stakeholders.

The expert panel questioned the overemphasis on identifiability and protection of privacy within regulations, particularly in the context of genomic data. Some experienced first-hand how this had hindered research. They agreed that sharing of data and transnational transfer are essential to capitalize maximally on genomic research. They further argued that instead of rigid requirements of privacy, regulators and bioethicists should prescribe safeguards against harms that may ensue from identifiability and breaching of privacy. For example; if the harm is authorities accessing sensitive information and using those for persecution, measures should be in place to prohibit a government or a law enforcement to use data of research participants for persecution.

4.3.2 Broad Consent

⁵³European Parliament and Council of European Union, 2016/679 <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-4-gdpr/>

⁵⁴Ibid. <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/>

⁵⁵ Mitchell, Colin, Johan Ordish and Alison Hall, op.cit., 2020.

⁵⁶ Rodriguez, Laura L, et al., "The Complexities of Genomic Identifiability", *Science*, Vol. 339, No. 6117, 2013, pp. 275-276.

⁵⁷ Finnegan, T and A Hall, "Identification and Genomic Data", *Cambridge, UK: PHG Foundation*, 2017, pp. 1- 45.

⁵⁸ Mitchell, Colin, Johan Ordish and Alison Hall, "Genomic Medicine and Research: When Does the GDPR Apply?", 2019, pp. 1-17.

⁵⁹ Mitchell, Colin, Johan Ordish and Alison Hall, op.cit., 2020.

⁶⁰ Phillips, Mark, Fruzsina Molnár-Gábor, Jan O Korbelt, Adrian Thorogood, Yann Joly, Don Chalmers, David Townend and Bartha M Knoppers, op.cit., 2020.

A broad consent refers to a consent form to which research participants can agree to future, yet unspecified research. Nevertheless, the process constitutes delegating some of the decision making to an independent oversight body, usually a research ethics committee and the commitment to ongoing future communication with research participants or donors of biospecimens⁶¹. GDPR permits the use of a broad consent so far as “it may be impossible to fully specify the precise purposes of any data processing in advance. Therefore, data subjects should be allowed to give their consent to certain areas of scientific research when in keeping with recognised ethical standards for scientific research”⁶².

Some studies showed that research participants indicated their unwillingness to the use of their samples in “research involving human cloning, research involving indigenous peoples, and possibly commercial or for-profit research”^{63,64,65,66,67}. Furthermore, it has been shown that research participants are not so much concerned with the specific purpose of a planned project but more concerned about the protection of their personal data against unauthorized use⁶⁸. Broad consent may on this background imply an expansive description of the purpose of research, e.g.: cancer research or research on rare diseases, but involve a more specific description regarding the processes of research, e.g.: collaboration with sharing of data across national borders, collaboration with commercial entities or use of genomic analyses.

For an international CoC, broad consent provides an alternative that is viewed as practical but still lacks structure as to its prerequisites. Furthermore, there are challenges to keep data subjects abreast with information regarding new studies that make use of their data⁶⁹.

⁶¹ Grady, Christine, et al., "Broad Consent for Research with Biological Samples: Workshop Conclusions", *The American Journal of Bioethics*, Vol. 15, No. 9, 2015, pp. 34-42.

⁶² Molnár-Gábor, Fruzsina and Jan O Korbel, op.cit., 2020.

⁶³ Brothers, Kyle B, Daniel R Morrison and Ellen W Clayton, "Two Large-Scale Surveys on Community Attitudes toward an Opt-out Biobank", *American journal of medical genetics Part A*, Vol. 155, No. 12, 2011, pp. 2982-2990.

⁶⁴ Gaskell, George, et al., "Publics and Biobanks: Pan-European Diversity and the Challenge of Responsible Innovation", *European Journal of Human Genetics*, Vol. 21, No. 1, 2013, pp. 14-20.

⁶⁵ Mccarty, Catherine A, et al., "Community Consultation and Communication for a Population-Based DNA Biobank: The Marshfield Clinic Personalized Medicine Research Project", *American journal of medical genetics Part A*, Vol. 146, No. 23, 2008, pp. 3026-3033.

⁶⁶ Stegmayr, Birgitta and Kjell Asplund, "Informed Consent for Genetic Research on Blood Stored for More Than a Decade: A Population Based Study", *Bmj*, Vol. 325, No. 7365, 2002, pp. 634-635.

⁶⁷ Tupasela, Aaro, et al., "Attitudes Towards Biomedical Use of Tissue Sample Collections, Consent, and Biobanks among Finns", *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*, Vol. 38, No. 1, 2010, pp. 46-52.

⁶⁸ Hoeyer, Klaus. "Denmark at a Crossroad? Intensified Data Sourcing in a Research Radical Country", in *The Ethics of Biomedical Big Data*. Springer, 2016, pp 73-93.

⁶⁹ Phillips, Mark, Fruzsina Molnár-Gábor, Jan O Korbel, Adrian Thorogood, Yann Joly, Don Chalmers, David Townsend and Bartha M Knoppers, op.cit., 2020.

The expert panel reflected on other models of consent as alternatives to individualized informed consent, some experts mentioned familial consent in the context of genomic data while other discussed broad consent. According to respondents, the former is a type of consent that has been used in the context of rare disease research where results were returned to family members of research participants. Using familial consent in genomic research would warrant some cultural context and sociological research particularly in across-borders data transfer. The research should address cultural nuances of what family is, sensitive information and data sharing. With regards to broad consent, they reiterated what the literature discussed in terms of defining requirements for a broad consent and creating processes to support participants' input and preferences.

4.3.3 Return of findings, portability and access

Participants' right to access of genomic data has been debated for some time now. These include discussions of return of uninterpreted data as well as clinically valid and actionable data. While some form of consensus has been reached in the return of incidental findings as to fulfil certain criteria; upon participants' approval (see for example Johansson et al.⁷⁰); and clinically valid and actionable results^{71,72}, the access to "uninterpreted" genetic data is still being debated. However, there are legal as well as ethical foundations that support such access whether in the context of clinical care or genetic research. Commentators described a few limitations to such rights: Risks of serious harm to data subject; to protect confidentiality and privacy and if involving excessive labour^{73,74}.

An international CoC, according to Phillips and colleagues⁷⁵, should address an optimal way for data subjects to access and transfer their genomic data securely as well as procedures for responsible disclosure of research or health findings. These questions, together with the right of access, return of results and portability were addressed during discussions with the expert panel.

According to them, the right to access incorporated two aspects; access to information about one's data processing and sharing, and the right to acquire a copy of one's data. The expert panel reflected

⁷⁰ Johansson, Jennifer Viberg, et al., "Research Participants' Preferences for Receiving Genetic Risk Information: A Discrete Choice Experiment", *Genetics in Medicine*, Vol. 21, No. 10, 2019, pp. 2381-2389.

⁷¹ Green, Robert C, et al., "Acmg Recommendations for Reporting of Incidental Findings in Clinical Exome and Genome Sequencing", *ibid.* Vol. 15, No. 7, 2013, pp. 565-574.

⁷² Hehir-Kwa, Jayne Y, et al., "Towards a European Consensus for Reporting Incidental Findings During Clinical Ngs Testing", *European Journal of Human Genetics*, Vol. 23, No. 12, 2015, pp. 1601-1606.

⁷³ Thorogood, Adrian, et al., "Applaud: Access for Patients and Participants to Individual Level Uninterpreted Genomic Data", *Human genomics*, Vol. 12, No. 1, 2018, pp. 1 - 6.

⁷⁴ Narayanasamy, Shaman, et al., "Genomic Sequencing Capacity, Data Retention, and Personal Access to Raw Data in Europe", *Frontiers in Genetics*, Vol. 11, No. 303, 2020, pp. 1- 15.

⁷⁵ Phillips, Mark, Fruzsina Molnár-Gábor, Jan O Korbelt, Adrian Thorogood, Yann Joly, Don Chalmers, David Townend and Bartha M Knoppers, *op.cit.*, 2020.

on the ethical permissibility of returning of results as well as its feasibility. Practically, the process would inadvertently involve identification and tracking of subjects' data, which would compromise privacy and confidentiality. Thus, in practice, the right to access can challenge the right to privacy. Some suggested a data protection impact analysis (DPIA) (This has been suggested by Art 35 of GDPR)⁷⁶ as part of the data management plan to determine the risks of procedures to return results and access of data.

There was a general consensus among the experts in response to portability of data query. For data subjects to make use of their genomic findings, there should be some flexibility to move their data around. They proposed technical tools that would provide secure, user friendly and interoperable platforms. However, whenever vulnerabilities in security of data exist, transparent communication of the risks to users is vital to maintain trust.

In response to what constitutes "responsible communication" of these findings, the members in the expert panel stated; first, a data subject/ patient indicates their preference to receive findings; secondly a decision is made of whether the findings are of clinical utility and actionability to data subjects; thirdly ensuring communication of good quality data (accurate and reliable); and lastly, advice on professional support should be given e.g.: a genetic counsellor, or a General Practitioner. A distinction was made between patients and volunteers donating their data or biospecimens in regards to their expectations. Patients might expect to receive relevant findings but volunteers may not.

4.3.4 Withdrawal of consent

Conventionally, withdrawal of consent has been an essential pillar in human subject research and was clearly stated in informed consent documents as a valid choice for research participants⁷⁷. However, guaranteeing withdrawal of consent becomes tricky in genomic therapies and diagnostics, since the genetic sequence of patients or volunteers can be incorporated in these new treatments or investigative tools. A famous example is HeLa cells⁷⁸.

GDPR states beyond doubt that informed consent, as a legal basis, must contain provisions to allow data subjects' withdrawal of consent within scientific research and other types of data processing (GDPR Art 7(3))⁷⁹. The GDPR demonstrates flexibility in providing the controller with other legal alternatives to informed consent (for example, "performance of a task carried out in the public

⁷⁶European Parliament and Council of European Union, 2016/679 <https://gdpr.eu/article-35-impact-assessment/>

⁷⁷ Van Delden, Johannes Jm and Rieke Van Der Graaf, "Revised Cioms International Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research Involving Humans", *Jama*, Vol. 317, No. 2, 2017, pp. 135-136.

⁷⁸ Nature, *Henrietta Lacks: Science Must Right a Historical Wrong*, 2020.
<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-02494-z>.

⁷⁹ European Parliament and Council of European Union, 2016/679

interest” (Art 6 (1e)) and other means (such as data processing for “medical or public health purposes”) Art 9 (2j)) to process genomic research⁸⁰. Thus, the right to be forgotten or erasure and the right to object can be limited in genomic research when such rights would adversely tamper the research process⁸¹.

The pressing issues that would need to be addressed in an international CoC with respect to withdrawal of consent are: How researchers can fulfil research subjects’ withdrawal of data from genomic databases; how aggregate data would be managed and; creating a system to notify third parties of data withdrawal⁸².

Most respondents in the expert panel agreed that aggregate data is anonymized data per GDPR and therefore need not be considered for withdrawal of consent. Yet the opinion was to ensure transparency at the onset of genomic research or genomic data processing endeavour, in conveying all the restrictions (e.g., in stem cell therapies) and prerequisites to all data subjects of when withdrawal of consent can and cannot be granted. In addition, they expressed that a contact person should be assigned to take charge of protection of such rights for instance, a Data Protection Officer (DPO). Some members suggested to implement “privacy by design methods” to infrastructures, such as cloud computing, where systems have in-built privacy protection measures and consequently reduce the burden of privacy protection on researchers.

To ensure withdrawal of consent and data from third parties, the suggestion was to implement “data mapping” of all third parties involved, extent of their data acquisition, information on onward data transfers etc. Data access committees (DAC) should establish clear and transparent structures and policies that include formal requests to third parties, maintain a catalogue of responses and actions taken by third parties and communicate the results to data subjects.

4.3.5 Compelled disclosure

Compelled disclosure is a situation when a government authority requests access to personal or health related data of research subjects and/or data subjects⁸³. In the US, there are special protections provided at the federal and/or the state level against compelled disclosure with regards to divulging research subjects’ information. The National Institute of Health can issue ‘certificate of confidentiality’, which shields research participants confidential information given during the course of research. These certificates are applicable on a federal level and on many occasions have safeguarded against courts

⁸⁰ Mitchell, Colin, Johan Ordish and Alison Hall, op.cit., 2020.

⁸¹ Bovenberg, Jasper, et al., "How to Fix the GDPR's Frustration of Global Biomedical Research", *Science*, Vol. 370, No. 6512, 2020, pp. 40-42.

⁸² Phillips, Mark, Fruzsina Molnár-Gábor, Jan O Korbelt, Adrian Thorogood, Yann Joly, Don Chalmers, David Townsend and Bartha M Knoppers, op.cit., 2020.

⁸³ Ibid.

demands of such information. However, concerns have been raised regarding conditions for waiver of confidentiality, the extent of the concept of identifiability, ambiguity of some definitions and the scope of these certificates ⁸⁴.

Furthermore, the certificates can be challenged by the Patriot Act of 2001, which can oblige companies to share data with US authorities. For example, the National Security Agency (NSA) can issue an order for an American cloud company (such as Amazon or Google) to impart data of certain individuals. The injunction has a long reach because it is not confined to US territories only, it extends to data under American companies “control, custody and possession”⁸⁵. Therefore, it can include other geographical areas outside the US. Furthermore, the order is acquired by a secret court and the company for which the order is issued, is forbidden to disclose such a breach to its clients ⁸⁶.

Bennett and colleagues proposed tools to overcome or reconcile these conflicting laws and regulations. Some of them have been invalidated in the EU such as the safe harbour in October, 2015 ⁸⁷ and the Privacy Shield agreement in July, 2020 ⁸⁸, while others need further corroboration that they actually work. They include:

- Standard Contractual Clauses (SCC)
- Binding Corporate Rules. ⁸⁹

The European Data Protection Board (EDPB) proposed SCC as a legal method to limit data access requests by local law enforcement authorities (for e.g., NSA in USA). These SCC would mandate that companies use technical processes such as “encryption, pseudo-anonymisation or split processing of data” to restrict access⁹⁰. Data importers (e.g., in the USA) are compelled to report data access requests (or actual data breaches) by local authorities or their failure to fulfil any related contractual

⁸⁴ Bennett, Steven C, M James Daley and Natascha Gerlach, "Storm Clouds Gathering for Cross-Border Discovery and Data Privacy: Cloud Computing Meets the USA Patriot Act", *Sedona Conf. J.*, Vol. 13, 2012, pp. 235-252.

⁸⁵ Ibid.

⁸⁶ Ibid.

⁸⁷ Monteleone, Shara and Laura Puccio, "From Safe Harbour to Privacy Shield: Advances and Shortcomings of the New EU-US Data Transfer Rules", *European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS)*, 2017, pp. 1-39.

⁸⁸ Jacques, René Z, 2020. <https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/upload/docs/application/pdf/2020-07/cp200091en.pdf>.

⁸⁹ Bennett, Steven C, M James Daley and Natascha Gerlach, op.cit., 2012.

⁹⁰ EDPB, *EDPB Recommendations, Supplementary Measures Transfers Tools Ensure Compliance with the EU Level Protection of Personal Data*, 2020.

https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/edpb/files/consultation/edpb_recommendations_202001_supplementarymeasurereansferstools_en.pdf.

agreements to data exporters (e.g., an EU country). Moreover, data importers should provide legal support and means of challenging public authorities' data access requests⁹¹.

According to EDPB, split processing of data means:

“The data exporter wishes personal data to be processed jointly by two or more independent processors located in different jurisdictions without disclosing the content of the data to them. Prior to transmission, it splits the data in such a way that no part an individual processor receives suffices to reconstruct the personal data in whole or in part. The data exporter receives the result of the processing from each of the processors independently, and merges the pieces received to arrive at the final result, which may constitute personal or aggregated data” EDPB, p.25)⁹²

In an answer to compelled disclosure, the expert panel had several suggestions; some of which were legal while others practical. While the former reflected many of the recommendations of the EDPB, one expert suggested that foreign law authority requiring access to protected data should do so through legal channels, i.e.: contacting local authorities of the data subject to obtain authorization. Functional suggestions included that the EU data can be located in GDPR friendly territories or where adequacy agreements exist with the host country (please see above for a list of GDPR friendly countries).

In SIENNA D 5.6 there has been a recommendation to create an international agreement at the level of the UN which can address data transfer (and problems related) across borders. The authors wrote:

“An international treaty⁹³ that addresses inter alia data sharing for scientific research and human genome modification, as well as introduces a right to (gen)omic information”⁹⁴ page 23.

We propose a further step ahead: To establish a unit or a committee within the UN which would be entrusted to formulate transnational legal avenues that could solve legal obstacles that currently exist to data use, transfer and sharing. Thus, the unit could provide legal solutions to some of the issues we raised in this report including compelled disclosure.

⁹¹ Ibid.

⁹² Ibid.

⁹³ See in that regard also a call from International Bioethics Committee on a treaty for genome editing, see UNESCO International Bioethics Committee (IBC), Report of the IBC on Updating Its Reflection on the Human Genome and Human Rights, SHS/YES/IBC-22/15/2 REV.2, Paris 2015.

⁹⁴ Siemaszko, Konrad , Rowena Rodrigues and Santa Slokenberga, op.cit., 2020. pp 23. [DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4121082](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4121082)

4.3.6 Cloud computing

A genomic cloud computing system is defined as “a scalable service where genetic sequence information is stored and processed virtually (i.e., in the ‘cloud’) usually via networked, large-scale data centres accessible remotely through various clients and platforms over the Internet”⁹⁵. Researchers can access and handle petabytes (1000 gigabyte) of data from their local office or lab. This is in contrast to a setting that was previously employed, where research institutes shopped local servers to store and process their data. The technology prides itself as being “locationless”, however, privacy laws and regulations are still location-bound and country specific⁹⁶.

Currently, there are 4 different models of installation of cloud computing as described by Dove et al.,⁹⁷ and Langmead and Nellore⁹⁸, namely;

- Commercial ones, such as Amazon and Google, open to the general public for use in return for a fee. Clients build, manage and scale it according to their wishes. They are the type mostly utilized in transnational genomic projects.
- Community ones which are used by a group of clients with specific shared interests.
- Hybrid infrastructure which is a combination of other types of cloud computing infrastructures.
- Private infrastructure used by one company serving numerous clients.

These infrastructures are supplied by a cloud service provider (CSP), which together with a client should agree on Terms of Service (ToS) via either a negotiable contract or a standard non-negotiable one. The common practice is that research institutes agree to the standard contract^{99,100}.

Among the advantages that cloud computing have over traditional local servers are: Relatively affordable since it reduces the expenditure for research institutes and allow researchers the flexibility to choose specific services from third parties (this function has been called elasticity); global accessibility; reproducibility (since researchers use the same IT tools as provided by cloud service); may

⁹⁵ Langmead, Ben and Abhinav Nellore, "Cloud Computing for Genomic Data Analysis and Collaboration", *Nature Reviews Genetics*, Vol. 19, No. 4, 2018, pp. 208 -220.

⁹⁶ Dove, Edward S, Yann Joly, Anne-Marie Tassé and Bartha M Knoppers, op.cit., 2015.

⁹⁷ Ibid.

⁹⁸ Langmead, Ben and Abhinav Nellore, op.cit., 2018.

⁹⁹ Dove, Edward S, Yann Joly, Anne-Marie Tassé and Bartha M Knoppers, op.cit., 2015.

¹⁰⁰ Langmead, Ben and Abhinav Nellore, op.cit., 2018.

have enhanced data security measures and lastly they are considered more environmentally friendly^{101, 102}.

Despite their advantages, the cloud computing commercial infrastructure raise major ethical and legal issues. Dove et al¹⁰³, discussed three major areas of concern namely; data control; data security, confidentiality and transfer; and lastly accountability. The authors also put forth recommendations to genomic researchers, which we believe are essential to take into account in a code of conduct for international data sharing. To avoid some of these concerns, academic cloud services are growing in number¹⁰⁴, which would enable researchers to have more control of data with no “commercial” third-party involvement.

The EU has published their own GDPR-friendly CoC on cloud computing which has been updated a few times since it was first published in 2016. The CoC is non obligatory and addresses primarily data processing between businesses, what is referred to “business to business (B2B) cloud computing”¹⁰⁵.

5. The Code of Conduct – A proposal

5.1 Preamble

The CoC is not a binding legal document but prescribes best practices for big data and cloud computing services. All activities within the SCOPE of this CoC are drafted and intended to be applied in line with the international standards for conducting research such as Declaration of Helsinki¹⁰⁶ and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights¹⁰⁷. Specific customizations, adaptations and adjustments may be necessary to respect local cultural and ethico-legal norms.

Scope

The target groups are stakeholders in the process: Researchers, controllers, Data Management Committees (DMC), Data Access Committees (DAC), cloud service providers and other stakeholders involved in processing of genomic data.

¹⁰¹ Ibid.

¹⁰² Dove, Edward S, Yann Joly, Anne-Marie Tassé and Bartha M Knoppers, op.cit., 2015.

¹⁰³ Ibid.

¹⁰⁴ Langmead, Ben and Abhinav Nellore, op.cit., 2018.

¹⁰⁵ The European Union, EU Cloud Code of Conduct, [European_Cloud_Code_of_Conduct_2.5.pdf](#)

¹⁰⁶ World Medical Association, "Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects", *Jama*, Vol. 310, No. 20, 2013, pp. 2191-2194.

¹⁰⁷ UN General Assembly, "Universal Declaration of Human Rights", *UN General Assembly*, Vol. 302, No. 2, 1948, pp. 14-25.

Purpose

This proposal of a CoC is developed for researchers/stakeholders who are conducting international genomic research and are utilizing or contributing to big databases which may incorporate cloud computing services.

5.2 Proposal for ethical principles for the CoC

The proposed ethical principles are well established and are featured in many ethical guidelines within the biomedical field. The principles listed below follow a hierarchy, where the first principle takes precedent over the second and the second principle ranks higher than the third one and so forth. They have been arranged according to their relative importance as judged by the lead authors of the report (AM & MH). Some of the principles are adopted from the American College of Epidemiology Policy Committee¹⁰⁸ while others adapted from guidelines of human subject research^{109, 110}.

- **Respect for persons:** This is achieved through informed consent procedures and respecting the privacy of data subjects and confidentiality of their data¹¹¹.
- **Beneficence and non-maleficence:** Research oversight, maximising benefits while minimising risks and transparency of communicating both risks and benefits of data sharing, are measures that fulfil beneficence and non-maleficence¹¹².
- **Protect and respect for vulnerable populations:** For groups and populations that have decreased capacity to give consent and are prone to exploitation, extra protections should be provided to safeguard their rights and wellbeing¹¹³.
- **“Freedom of scientific enquiry:** custodianship (stewardship) should encourage openness of scientific enquiry, and should maximize data use and sharing to the extent that it promotes health”¹¹⁴.
- **Transparency:** Researchers should communicate transparently their motivations and research plans with relevant stakeholders. Transparency should be a principle that is maintained

¹⁰⁸ Ness, Roberta B, "Biospecimen "Ownership": Point", *Cancer Epidemiology and Prevention Biomarkers*, Vol. 16, No. 2, 2007, pp. 188-189.

¹⁰⁹ van Delden, Johannes JM and Rieke van der Graaf, op.cit., 2017.

¹¹⁰ Emanuel, Ezekiel J, David Wendler and Christine Grady, "What Makes Clinical Research Ethical?", *ibid.* Vol. 283, No. 20, 2000, pp. 2701-2711.

¹¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹¹² *Ibid.*

¹¹³ van Delden, Johannes JM and Rieke van der Graaf, op.cit., 2017.

¹¹⁴ Hansson, Mats G, Beltran Sergi, Rachel Thompson and Jane Reichel, op.cit., 2018.

throughout the data cycle and include and not limited to communicating potential risks, respecting privacy and informing of unauthorized access to data.

- **Accountability:** The data cycle should have a clear chain of responsibility, where stakeholders such as researchers, data processors and controllers, have clearly defined functions and comply to legal and ethical regulations.
- **Fair share of benefits and non-exploitation.** Whenever data yields benefit in the form of new therapeutics or clinically actionable information, these should be shared fairly with local communities who donated their data when requested.
- **Community protection and engagement.** This is particularly relevant for data sharing involving minority groups. Whenever possible, local researchers and community leaders should be engaged in research endeavours since they can identify local research needs and best ways to protect data subjects.
- **“Attribution:** recognizing that the intellectual investment of investigators involved in the creation of data registries is often substantial, and could be acknowledged by mutual agreement” ¹¹⁵.
- **Data minimization:** “That the data you transferred are relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which it is transferred to and processed in the third country” ¹¹⁶.

¹¹⁵ Ibid.

¹¹⁶ EDPB, op.cit., 2020.

https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/edpb/files/consultation/edpb_recommendations_202001_supplementarymeasurereansferstools_en.pdf

Figure 3: The governance system for data-sharing

5.3 A proposal for an international code of conduct for data sharing in genomics.

5.3.1 A governance system

Article 1: A data governance system “specifies decision rights and accountabilities for an organization’s decision- making about its data. Furthermore, data governance formalizes data policies, standards, and procedures and monitors compliance” ¹¹⁷ (refer to diagram 3).

We suggest the formation of a data management committee (DMC) that establishes a governance system, which among other things, would oversee relationships with cloud service providers and review requests of transfer and share of data by researchers or research teams. For every project where data sharing is necessary or proposed, a request is reviewed by the DMC with the ultimate goal to pursue the FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability) of data use¹¹⁸. The DMC would have a Data Protection Officer (DPO), at least a patient group representative, a member from the research team, IT security personal, a bioinformatician, a bioethicist, a clinician and a public representative. The DMC would ensure the compliance to a robust governance system and guide those who are responsible to:

¹¹⁷ Abraham, Rene, Johannes Schneider and Jan Vom Brocke, "Data Governance: A Conceptual Framework, Structured Review, and Research Agenda", *International Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 49, 2019, pp. 424-438.

¹¹⁸ Wilkinson, Mark D, et al., "The Fair Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship", *Scientific data*, Vol. 3, No. 1, 2016, pp. 1-9.

- a- Establish Terms of reference (ToR) for use of cloud computing or big databases which include: Clear definitions of terminology, defined roles of stakeholders and harmonize terminology used among the stakeholders. Each defined role or function within the data cycle should include extent of data access, processing and sharing.
- b- Defining a chain of reporting and responsibility among stakeholders (users, processors of data, controllers, funders, cloud computing services providers etc..) in terms of data import and export, processing, access, return of data-processed findings and security.
- c- Establish an error management system and related standard operating procedures to report incidents of data breach or hacking or misuse or unauthorized access by law enforcement and third parties.
- d- Establish auditing systems both internally and externally to ensure compliance to ToR.
- e- “Set up procedures to resolve conflicts that arise between stakeholders and actors.
- f- Non-compliant partners should be stopped from using the databases” ¹¹⁹.
- g- Define research goals and direction
- h- Negotiate contracts with commercial cloud service providers, transfer and share of data upon requests by researchers or research teams.

5.3.2 Data collection

Article 2: Researcher should ensure that data subjects (patients, volunteers and/or research participants) receive *sufficient* information as defined by the local legal regime. Informed consent offered should depend on the nature and type of research, whether a protocol which can be disease/context/ sub-population specific or very broad i.e., creating a data resource/biobank for use by others. The data subject should obtain the following information:

- a- “Data controller/s information and contact details.
- b- Voluntary nature of data or sample donation.
- c- The purposes (specific or broad according to the nature of research) of the processing including possibility of secondary use of data, if needed.
- d- Potential risks to identifiability of processed data.

¹¹⁹World Health Organization, op.cit., 2019.

- e- The likelihood of transnational data transfers as well as secondary transfer.
- f- If complementary information will be added through linkage to different data registries, medical records, etc.
- g- Methods of funding whether academic or mixed model funding with commercial entities.
- h- The process for reporting of research results and incidental findings (refer to article 7 for more details)
- i- That consent may be withdrawn and how this is done.” (refer to article 5 for more details (adapted from RD- connect, 2018)) ¹²⁰.
- j- Reconsent procedures from children and new-borns who have had their genomic data collected, when they come of legal age. Also, participants who are engaged in long term cohorts should reconsent periodically (for example every 10-15 years).
- k- How records of consent, reconsent are maintained and kept up to date.

Article 3: Any consent form and process should comply to international ethical requirements and should be approved by the local research ethics committee. Other models of consent such as familial¹²¹ or dynamic consent ¹²² should be adapted and adopted as alternatives to accommodate cultural and social differences as well as nature of research (see article 2 above).

Article 4: To fulfil broad consent requirements:

- a- Researchers should develop tools (a platform with a notification alert to new projects whenever a donor sample is used) for keeping donors/research participants informed about the types of research being conducted on their data.
- b- Researchers should conduct periodic re-assessment of attitudes and research preferences of the data subjects.
- c- Researchers should be aware that broad consent can differ across geographical areas since research should have a social value for the targeted community.

¹²⁰Hansson, Mats G, Beltran Sergi, Rachel Thompson and Jane Reichel, op.cit., 2018. https://rd-connect.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/RD-Connect_Code-of-Conduct_GPAP_20180525.pdf

¹²¹ Nguyen, Minh Thu, et al., "Model Consent Clauses for Rare Disease Research", *BMC medical ethics*, Vol. 20, No. 1, 2019, pp. 55.

¹²² Budin-Ljøsne, Isabelle, et al., "Dynamic Consent: A Potential Solution to Some of the Challenges of Modern Biomedical Research", *ibid.* Vol. 18, 2017, pp. 1-10.

- d- Data collectors/researchers should record and report patients' or data subjects' preferences (e.g.: to participate in only certain types of research) to their data use. This would warrant extra resources and an ongoing communication with data subjects.

Article 5: Researchers should enable the option of withdrawal of consent to data use in research – which is limited by:

- a- If it is practically impossible to withdraw the data (data has been used to manufacture therapies or diagnostics – e.g.: cell cultures, stem cell therapies).
- b- If it would critically impact the purpose to which data was processed.
- c- If the data has been aggregated.

In situations where withdrawal of consent is set up, researchers shall create the appropriate channels of communications and reporting to data subjects, third parties, and data processors to ensure withdrawal of data from all partners.

Article 6: Researchers should ensure the quality of the data used in their research projects by complying to international standards.

Article 7: Researchers should return genomic data findings to data subjects, while explaining the risks that are associated with such reidentification. The measures should be appropriated to local healthcare and legal systems. To return the findings researchers should

- a- Return findings to data subjects who indicated their interest to receive findings and in keeping with local healthcare and legal systems.
- b- Return findings that are clinically valid, actionable and have been confirmed by a clinical laboratory.
- c- Recommend that data subjects seek professional advice such as a genetic counsellor or their General Practitioner.
- d- If clearly stated in the research protocol and research participants request uninterpreted data for diagnostic purposes, researchers might provide secure, user-friendly and interoperable platforms i.e., presented in a language and a format that can be machine and human readable¹²³.

¹²³ Wilkinson, Mark D, Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, Jan-Willem Boiten, Luiz Bonino da Silva Santos and Philip E Bourne, op.cit., 2016.

5.3.3 Data storage.

Article 8: Data collected can be stored in local servers, international and/or cloud computing services (commercial, academic or public). Whatever the platform used, researchers should ensure security and safety of data are maintained.

5.3.3.1 Cloud computing storage

For the purpose of this CoC, the focus will be on best practices of cloud computing storage. All the rules in this section have been adapted from recommendations by Dove and colleagues ¹²⁴.

Article 9: Research institutions should as much as possible opt for academic cloud services, or cloud services that can abide by SCC, whenever possible and feasible.

Article 10: When using commercial cloud services, research institutions/data management committees should arrange for negotiable contracts with commercial CSPs and avoid standard predetermined contracts.

Article 11: To negotiate Terms of Service (ToS) with CSP, data management committees/research institutes should have,

- a- Amendments to ToS:
 - Clear procedures for proper notification of amendments in ToS including allocating adequate time for response and acceptance by cloud users ¹²⁵.
- b- Support and maintenance
 - Clear instructions on upholding confidentiality of genomic data, while CSPs conduct their support activities such as maintenance of cloud computing service.
 - Restrict CSP monitoring of stored data.
 - Clear safeguards against data breaches, damage or loss of data.
- c- Deletion of data and cloud exit strategies
 - Unambiguous provisions on data deletion, including backups and duplicates, and duration of the grace period (if applicable) and incurred costs for data deletion in the event of CSP contract termination.
 - State the agreed grace period where data is kept on the cloud after contract termination.

¹²⁴ Dove, Edward S, Yann Joly, Anne-Marie Tassé and Bartha M Knoppers, op.cit., 2015.

¹²⁵ Ibid.

- Clauses that researchers can retrieve stored and processed genomic data and that a CSP cannot retain it or use it after the contract ends.
 - Clear provisions for exit strategies are stated and agreed upon in the event that a cloud service is acquired by a third party.
- d- Data privacy and confidentiality
- Agreement to treat health and genomic data as “special type of data” that warrants extra security measures and protection of confidentiality.
 - Provisions on data encryption, while at rest and as it is being transferred.

Article 12: Researchers should limit authorizing access to cloud services or genomic database to only members of the research team conducting research (e.g.: technicians, bioinformaticians, research assistants) who have been approved by a DMC or a DAC ¹²⁶.

Article 13: Researchers should only deposit encrypted data for storage in a database or a cloud computing service and ensure there are regular back up of the data. For traceability, all submitted datasets are linked to the username of the data submitter within the system ¹²⁷.

Article 14: In cases of breaches to data safety (e.g.: data losses or damage) or security (unauthorized access), the CSP should notify researchers within a brief specified period.

5.3.4 Data sharing, transfer and access

Article 15: To share or transfer or exchange data, researchers must do so by using minimal data for the purpose, encrypting genomic data and only using secure channels that are protected against unauthorized access.

Article 16: Researchers should transfer data that are relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which it is transferred and processed.

Article 17: Researchers should maintain records of data transferral, users’ activity and logging to the database or cloud service for auditing purposes and accountability ¹²⁸.

¹²⁶ BBMRI-ERIC, op.cit., 2017. https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/wp-content/uploads/AoM_10_8_Access-Policy_FINAL_EU.pdf

¹²⁷ Hansson, Mats G, Beltran Sergi, Rachel Thompson and Jane Reichel, op.cit., 2018. https://rd-connect.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/RD-Connect_Code-of-Conduct_GPAP_20180525.pdf

¹²⁸ Ibid.

Article 18: Data protection officer should, in coordination with CSPs and researchers, decide to store data and applications only in designated regions, where there are adequacy decisions or compatible regulations to national laws¹²⁹.

Article 19: Data access committees or data management committees should evaluate requests for data access, exchange and transfer and validate requester's identity, credentials and research goals. They should ascertain that researchers will abide by the code of conduct, relevant laws or adherence agreements.

Article 20: Proper attribution and intellectual property should be accorded as appropriate. Sharing of data shall follow criteria for the acknowledgement of intellectual contributions and originality through rules of authorship and intellectual property rights¹³⁰.

5.3.5. Compelled disclosure

Article 21: Any requests of unauthorized data access by law enforcement or national security agents of a foreign country for example data importers, without data subject knowledge should be barred by CSP or DMC. This should be clearly stated in ToS and SCCs.

5.3.6 Data handling from LMIC

Article 22: The local values, cultures and customs should be respected throughout the data processing activities (e.g., data collection, transferring etc.). To that respect, transparency of the research procedures and methods, as well as of the scientific goals, is essential for enhancing community engagement and building trust between researchers and local groups (Refer to article 3).

5.3.7 Public and community engagement

Article 23: A community is defined by a disease, an age group, a geographical location, a culture and an ethnicity. Measures should be taken to actively engage communities and data subjects. This can be achieved through:

- a- involving members of specific communities, patient groups and the public in DMC (refer to a governance system article 1) depending on the type and nature of research.
- b- Periodically assessing data subjects' attitudes and research preferences (refer to broad consent article 4).
- c- As members of research ethics committees when specific research protocols address particular communities (e.g., indigenous groups).

¹²⁹ Dove, Edward S, Yann Joly, Anne-Marie Tassé and Bartha M Knoppers, op.cit., 2015.

¹³⁰ Hansson, Mats G, Beltran Sergi, Rachel Thompson and Jane Reichel, op.cit., 2018.

6. Conclusion

In a fast evolving and big multi -omics data environment, many traditional methods of overseeing human subject research are being questioned for effectiveness and functionality. Bioethicists and regulators are adapting by incorporating new ways of ethical oversight. For example, the adoption of new models of obtaining data subject consent such as broad¹³¹, dynamic¹³² and familial¹³³ consent.

Taking into account the current tools at hand and how rapidly information technologies are evolving, it is not a far-fetched vision that data subjects would increasingly have more control over their donated data and attain a more flexible approach to harness their data within big data research. They could access digital platforms, where they can “shop” for the type of consent they prefer, or the type of research they would like their data to contribute to, or select specific academic, commercial and more commonly mixed partners to process their data. Furthermore, they can indicate the countries where they are willing to transfer their data, or the type of databases crosslinking to their genomic information, or the type of customized findings they wish to be informed about. Additionally, data subjects and local communities will become a more integral part of setting the research agenda and ensuring fairer share of benefits.

We propose this CoC which we view as a first step to a more detailed and comprehensive document on best practices for big databases and genomic data-sharing globally. The document may warrant other revisions and adjustments, especially to accommodate European laws such as GDPR. Our proposal is to found an international unit at the UN, which can formulate legal avenues that organise big data transfers transnationally and resolve conflicting laws and regulations regarding privacy and IP laws, among others.

¹³¹ Grady, Christine, Lisa Eckstein, Ben Berkman, Dan Brock, Robert Cook-Deegan, Stephanie M Fullerton, Hank Greely, Mats G Hansson, Sara Hull and Scott Kim, *op.cit.*, 2015.

¹³² Budin-Ljøsne, Isabelle, Harriet JA Teare, Jane Kaye, Stephan Beck, Heidi Beate Bentzen, Luciana Caenazzo, Clive Collett, Flavio D’Abramo, Heike Felzmann and Teresa Finlay, *op.cit.*, 2017.

¹³³ Nguyen, Minh Thu, Jack Goldblatt, Rosario Isasi, Marlene Jagut, Anneliene Hechtelt Jonker, Petra Kaufmann, Laetitia Ouillade, Fruszina Molnar-Gabor, Mahsa Shabani and Eric Sid, *op.cit.*, 2019.

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Legislative documents

European Parliament and Council of European Union, General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679
<https://gdpr-info.eu/>

The European Union, EU Cloud Code of Conduct, *European_Cloud_Code_of_Conduct_2.5.pdf*

Annexes

Annex 1

SIENNA Project Workshop September, 2020

Objectives

This workshop will allow for the researchers working on SIENNA WP2 - on the ELSI of Human Genomics- to obtain expert views on two reports: First one addresses a proposal for operational guidelines for ethical self- assessment of research in genetics and genomics and the second report tackles a proposal/review for an international code of conduct for data sharing in genomics. The reports fulfil the deliverables for tasks 2.7 (ethical frameworks), and 5.2 (code of conduct in genomics). In doing so, we will also look forward to and ask from participants to consider the challenges and policy needs that go along with these reports.

The SIENNA project - *Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact* - has received funding under the European Union's [H2020 research and innovation programme](#) under grant agreement No 741716.

Disclaimer: This workshop and its contents reflects only SIENNA's view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Day 1: Thursday 10 September, 2020

Location: via Zoom

15:00 – 15:15	Welcome and introduction to SIENNA, overview of goals of workshops Mats Hansson, Uppsala University
Session 1: A proposal for operational guidelines for ethical self- assessment of research in genetics and genomics Chair: Mats Hansson, Uppsala University	
15:20 – 15: 40	Discussant 1: Martina C Cornel, Amsterdam University Medical Center
15:40 – 16: 00	Discussant 2: Olga Tzortzatou, Biomedical Research Foundation of the Academy of Athens
16:00 – 16: 45	Open discussion with all participants
16:45 – 17: 00	Short recap of the day and final remarks

Day 2: Friday 11 September, 2020

Location: via Zoom

15:00 – 15:15	Welcome and introduction to SIENNA, overview of goals of the session Mats Hansson, Uppsala University
Session 2: A Proposal for an International Code of Conduct for Data sharing in Genomics Chair: Amal Matar, Uppsala University	
15:20 – 15: 40	Discussant 1: Stefan Eriksson, Uppsala University
15:40 – 16: 00	Discussant 2: Elias Uhlin, CCRM, Canada
16:00 – 16: 45	Group discussion with all participants
16:45 – 17: 00	Short recap of the day and final remarks

List of Participants

	Name	Organisation
1	Martina C Cornel	Amsterdam University Medical Center
2	Elias Uhlin	CCRM, Canada
3	Stefan Eriksson	Uppsala University
4	Olga Tzortzatou	Biomedical Research Foundation of the Academy of Athens
5	Kärt Pormeister	University of Tartu
6	Gauthier Chassang	INSERM
7	Antonella Cardone	European Cancer Patient Coalition
8	Manuel Guerrero	Uppsala University
9	Adam Panagiotopoulos	Trilateral Research
10	Jantina De Vries	University of Cape Town
11	Adrian Mark Thorogood	McGill U, University of Luxembourg
12	Josepine Fernow	Uppsala University
13	Anna Holm	Uppsala University
14	Amal Matar	Uppsala University
15	Mats Hansson	Uppsala University
16	Philip Hoevel	European Network of Research Ethics Committees
17	Michael Beauvais	McGill University
18	Santa Slokenberga	Uppsala University